

ASSESSMENT OF LEADERSHIP QUALITY AMONG SOUTH ZONE INTER UNIVERSITY PLAYERS OF DIFFERENT GAMES

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to comparative study on leadership quality among the South Zone Inter University players of various games namely basketball, volleyball and handball. To achieve the purpose, 15 players from all the three games (N = 45) were selected from South Zone Inter University tournaments. The first group with basketball players, the second group with volleyball players and the third group with handball players. Blake and Mouton Managerial Grid Leadership Self-Assessment Questionnaire was used to collect data on leadership quality. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistical technique was used analyse the data. The results of the study clearly showed that there was significant difference among players of various games in leadership quality. The study also revealed that basketball players had team leader quality while other team players had authoritarian quality.

Key Words: Basketball, Volleyball, Handball, Leadership Quality

1. Introduction:

Sports are a dynamic social force in our culture. Sports have become an important part of the culture of the nations throughout the world. A good leader should be aware of opinions, feelings and characteristics of those working with him. He should have the quality to judge the feelings and needs of others. A good leader should have a strong will power and should not be a fickle minded person. (Uppal, A.K, et.al., 2004)

Personality is the sum of activities that can be discovered by actual observations over a long enough period of time to give reliable information. Personality is a dynamic organization within the individual of those Psycho-physical systems that determine his unique adjustment to his environment.

Personality is made up of a number of elements such as personal appearance, physical constitution, knowledge experience, intelligence, character, habits, temperament, attitudes and beliefs. (Geetha Mathew, 1997).

Many sports psychologists have studied the relationship between personality and sports performance. Various researchers have reported that athletes or players are more independent, objective, self-confident, competitive, outgoing or extroverted and less anxious than nonathletes. (Wuest, Deboran A, et.al., 1992).

Authoritarian Leader who are the people who get this rating are very much task oriented and are hard on their workers. There is little or no allowance for cooperation or collaboration. Heavily task oriented people display these characteristics: they are very strong on schedules; they expect people to do what they are told without question or debate. So, it is difficult for their subordinates to contribute or develop.

Team Leader who are the people leads by positive example and endeavors to foster a team environment in which all team members can reach their highest potential, both as team members and as people. They encourage the team to reach team goals as effectively as possible, while also working tirelessly to strengthen the bonds among the various members. They normally form and lead some of the most productive teams.

A leadership training effort must aim at developing qualities as courage, intelligence, confidence, daring, common sense, presence of mind, judgement, initiative, decision-making and so on. (Kamlesh M L., 2016).

2. Methodology:

To accomplish the aim of the study, forty-five players were selected randomly from various games namely basketball, volleyball and handball from the South Zone Inter University tournaments. 15 players of each game made as one group and all the three groups were given the Blake and Mouton Managerial Grid Leadership Self-Assessment Questionnaire to assess their leadership quality. The data which were collected from subjects were treated statistically. To find out the significance differences in leadership quality among the players of various games, one way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used as a statistical technique. To find out the paired mean differences, the Scheffe's s post test was used. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 level to test the significance.

3. Results and Discussion:

On the basis of statistical treatment on the collected data, the results on leadership quality presented in the below tables. This part deals with the analysis of data collected from the samples under study. This research was to compare the leadership quality among the South Zone Inter University players of various games namely basketball, volleyball and handball. To achieve the purpose of this study, 15 basketball players, 15 volleyball players and 15 handball players from South Zone Inter University tournament were selected. The subjects were selected at random; the selected subjects were evaluated on their leadership quality based on Blake and Mouton Managerial Grid Leadership Self-Assessment Questionnaire.

Table 1: Showing the Analysis of Variance on the Means obtained in from Different game players represented South Zone Inter University Tournaments in the Personality trait Leadership quality

	Basketball Group	Volleyball Group	Handball Group	Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	Obtained F-ratio
Mean	11.93	8.00	7.33	B	185.38	2	92.69	148.21*
				W	26.27	42	0.63	

Table F-ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 2 and 41 (df) = 3.22,
 2 and 42 df = 3.22

*: Significant

Table I shows the analyzed data on leadership quality. The test means of leadership quality were 11.93 for basketball group, 8.00 for volleyball group and 7.33 for handball group. The obtained F-ratio 148.21 was greater than the table F-ratio 3.22. Hence the test was insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 2 and 42.

Since there were significant differences among the players of different games of South Zone Inter University, Scheffe's post hoc test was used to find out the paired mean differences among the groups, which is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Showing Means, Mean Differences and the Required Value of Scheffe's Confidence Interval

Basketball Group	Volleyball Group	Handball Group	Mean Difference (MD)	C.I Value
11.93	8.00		3.93*	0.73
11.93		7.33	4.6*	
	8.00	7.33	0.67	

*: Significant

Table 2 shows the scheffe's post-hoc test of mean difference of leadership quality for different groups. The differences between the basketball group and volleyball group was 3.93, basketball group and handball group was 4.6 and volleyball group and handball group was 0.67. Hence, the first and second group comparisons were significant and third comparison was insignificant.

The analysis of variance of leadership quality indicated that basketball players had team leader quality whereas volleyball and handball players had authoritarian leader quality.

4. Conclusion:

Within the limitations and delimitations of this study, the following conclusions were arrived at:

- It was concluded that basketball players had team leader quality than volleyball and handball players.
- It was concluded that volleyball and handball players had authoritarian leader quality who were felt difficult with their subordinates to contribute.

5. References:

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